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Integral Education: Insights from Sri Aurobindo's Philosophy of Education and It's common aspects with NEP 2020

Dr. Aditi Dubey

Department of Humanities, University Institute of Technology. RGPV, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Aditi Dubey

Abstract

This article explores the relationship between educational philosophy of Sri Aurobindo and the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. Sri Aurobindo envisioned education as a holistic process that fosters physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual development. His approach emphasizes self-discovery, and the harmony which exist between the individual and the society, and the multidimensional nature of human beings. By aligning these principles with the objectives of NEP 2020, this article argues that Aurobindo's vision can enhance the policy's effectiveness and relevance. Sri Aurobindo gave a model of education that helps in transformation by nurturing personal growth of a person and also of the society.

Keywords: Integral, Education, Philosophy, NEP, Humanities

Introduction

Integral Education Philosophy by Sri Aurobindo's

Philosopher and a visionary thinker Sri Aurobindo contributed to politics, spirituality, and education. His revolutionary personality led him to become a spiritual guide. He regarded education as a powerful force for individual and national transformation. His concept of Integral Education reflects his belief in the overall and proper development of the-physical, emotional mental, psychological, and spiritual self of an individual.

Integral Education, as envisioned by Sri Aurobindo, presents a comprehensive framework for cultivating overall individual. Apart from academic achievements this framework emphasize the development of the body through physical activity, emotions through creativity and interpersonal relationships, the brain through critical and interdisciplinary thinking, and the spiritual self through self-introspection and learning which is value based.

He believed that education must foster self-discipline instead of rote learning inner development should be fostered through yoga, and the elevation of consciousness. Sri Aurobindo Ashram School at Pondicherry (now

Auroville), is a live example of value based, alternative learning model of education This model of education is a guideline for policy reforms aimed at aligning national education systems with the holistic needs of today's learners.

National Education Policy (NEP) 2020: A innovative concept and visionary idea to transform education system

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, introduced by the Government of India, adopts strategy to redesign the Indian education system according to global needs and local trends. It emphasizes learner-centric, experiential, and competency-based education while integrating digital literacy, vocational skills, and socio-emotional learning into the curriculum (Sarkar & Singh, 2020) [3].

The policy gives priority to literacy at foundation level. It emphasizes flexibility and multidisciplinary learning, technology enabled education, development of teacher, fostering of Indian languages and preservation of Indian culture, and the inculcation of creativity, research, and innovation. It also reinforces global engagement while being

rooted in Indian values.

NEP 2020 advocates an approach that is inclusive and is guided by access, equity, quality, and learning for a better life. Its objective is to train learners in an environment where they can have personalized learning. NEP 2020 aims to impart to learners experiential learning that will make them fit for a rapidly evolving workforce and knowledge society. To effectively implement NEP 2020, it is very important to collaborate institutes, redesign curriculum, reframe pedagogy enhance partnership for innovation.

Sri Aurobindo's Vision in implementation of NEP 2020

By incorporating Sri Aurobindo's concept of Integral Education, education system can be designed in a manner which is more centred towards humanistic approach and an experience which will transform the whole personality of learner. It will be a new educational experience.

Aurobindo's philosophy highlights intellectual excellence along with the edification of character, creativity, ethical integrity, and spiritual awareness. This framework of holistic development harmonizes with NEP's priority of critical thinking, creativity, and personal development.

Self-Discovery aspect in Educational Philosophy of Sri Aurobindo

Philosophy Sri Aurobindo of states that self-discovery should be the purpose of education. Education should help individuals realize their inner potential. Education should not merely impart knowledge. To achieve this the learners should have self-awareness. They should have the ability to reflect and have clarity of the purpose of their life. It also requires deeper understanding of their values and strengths.

Aurobindo's theory of Self-discovery motivates students to confront societal norms and reveal their own unique identity. Learners should know their aim of life. This concept strongly agrees with NEP 2020's aim of fostering creativity, critical thinking, and intrinsic motivation. This theory of education helps in achieving state of self-realization and authenticity.

Multidisciplinary Knowledge

Sri Aurobindo's Educational Philosophy and NEP200 both highlights the importance of integrating multidisciplinary knowledge and learning, NEP 2020 encourages multidisciplinary approach and flexible curriculum. Learners are allowed to pursue diverse learning areas to acquire knowledge and skills of their own interest and fields, areas where learners can evolve in a better way and can have lifelong learning. NEP 2020 have discarded traditional method of choosing particular combination of subjects, it now fosters study of various fields having creative combinations with an aim to develop well-rounded individuals with critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills.

Multidisciplinary learning approach broadens the thought process of the learner and brings clarity to all different aspects, issues for a better life of his own liking.

Sri Aurobindo's multidisciplinary approach of education system allows students to see connections between different subjects. By integrating different subjects of their own interest, students can learn to interpret life with their own perspective. Sri Aurobindo's philosophy and NEP 2020

both emphasize to create an environment for students where they can learn through self-experience inquisitiveness critical thinking. Students should have the mind-set of lifelong learning and should be able to adapt to a rapidly changing world. Education should empower them to deal life with wisdom and compassion and contribute for the betterment of the society.

Inclusion of Spiritual aspect in Education

According to Sri Aurobindo, inclusion of spirituality in education system is very essential for overall development. He believed that education is a medium to awaken higher consciousness, compassion, empathy, and moral clarity. His theory calls for integrating spiritual and ethical content into curricula, that will not only promote individual wellbeing of a person but also a collective responsible society. Though there is no direct emphasize of spirituality in NEP 2020, it has the same spirit of Integrating spirituality and value based education into education that will fosters a balanced mind set and harmonious social environment, echoing Sri Aurobindo's vision.

Integration of Indian traditional knowledge

Sri Aurobindo's philosophy strongly suggest that education should include Indian values traditions, languages, literature and should be rooted in nation's cultural and spiritual inheritance. NEP 2020 also focuses promoting cultural awareness and integrating India's rich heritage knowledge systems, and cultural ethos.

Conclusion

This paper supports contribution of the concept of traditional Indian educational ideas and ideas of integral education philosophy of Sri Aurobindo with modern concept of education system. Education system of 21st century can be transformed by aligning modern practices of education with cultural and philosophical traditions. By fostering comprehensive growth comprising cognitive, emotional, ethical and spiritual aspect by educators, a truly better new education system can be established

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